

Used Data Extraction Form

Information Type	Extracted Data
Reference Information	Title of document: Author(s): Publication Date: Source:
Information from RQ1 What are the challenges or problems of GSD presented?	
Information from RQ2 How were these challenges and problems defined/discovered?	
Information from RQ3 Does the proposal/approach use some tool/ software to support the GSD?	<input type="checkbox"/> YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO
Information from RQ4 Does the proposal/approach use some provenance model to support the GSD?	<input type="checkbox"/> YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO
Information from RQ5 How was the proposal/approach evaluated?	Evaluation Description: